

A PROOF-OF-CONCEPT FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A EUROPEAN COPERNICUS COASTAL FLOOD AWARENESS SYSTEM

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Users' Requirements Report

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Summary

Deliverable 2.3 – Users’ requirements report, a Deliverable of Task 2.3 – Collection of users’ requirements – reports on the end-user engagement. It follows Deliverable 2.1 – User inventory and engagement, and its objective has been to ascertain end-users’ requirements and needs in the development of a European Coastal Flood Awareness System. It involves a pool (sample) composed of 189 potential ECFAS end-users. An anonymous questionnaire was designed and activated online on an open-source internet survey tool to collect the end-users’ information. The information constituted a dataset on the end-users’ profile and their preferred technical specifications of the different components that form ECFAS. Apart from the questionnaire design, the work involved dataset management (creation of an executable program to facilitate data management and the creation of new – composite – variables), data quality control, and statistical analyses performed to describe the user pool. 117 end-users completed the questionnaire (62% response rate). The pool was mostly composed of respondents from public organisations based in Southern and Mediterranean European Countries. There is generally great support for the mapping products ECFAS will deliver. The specifications of the warning and mapping components indicated by the end-users are in agreement with the ECFAS initial specifications and are also integrated (when feasible) into the coastal flood warning system. Finally, it is submitted that the end-users’ engagement process, which has been supported by key facilitators (project partners, External Board Members), has been successful in achieving results that provided crucial information for the design of a coastal flood awareness system which will eventually be integrated into the Copernicus Emergency Management Service.

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List of Main Acronyms

C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CLS	Collecte Localisation Satellites
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
CUF	Copernicus User Forum
CP	Contracting Party
CSET	Core Services Exploitation Team
D	Deliverable
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
DRR	Disaster Risk Reduction
EBM	External Board Member
ECFAS	European Coastal Flood Awareness System
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EU	European Union
EWS	Early Warning System
FD	Floods Directive
FHRM	Flood Hazard and Flood Risk Map
FRMP	Flood Risk Management Plan
FP7	Seventh Framework Programme of the European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020 European Union Project
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IUSS	Istituto Universitario di Studi Superiori Pavia
NRA	National Risk Assessment
PKH	Planetek Hellas
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
PAEI	Public Access to Environmental Information
RM	Rapid Mapping
RRM	Risk and Recovery Mapping
SDS	Satellite-Derived Shoreline
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SD	Standard Deviation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SDT	Sustainable Development Target
SFDRR	Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction
SSL	Storm Surge Level
T	Task
TWL	Total Water Level
UAEGEAN	University of the Aegean
UCPM	Union Civil Protection Mechanism
USB	Users Board
UN	United Nations
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 The ECFAS project in brief

The ECFAS Project aims at contributing to the evolution of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (CEMS) by demonstrating the technical and operational feasibility of a European Coastal Flood Awareness System that will be relevant for the enhancement of the Service and will capitalise on the corresponding product portfolio and existing Copernicus Emergency Management Service – European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) framework. ECFAS will provide a proof-of concept (PoC) that will complement and broaden the currently available panoply of core service information. ECFAS tackles coastal resilience to marine storminess and population exposure in coastal areas prone to flooding. ECFAS will contribute to a fully integrated risk cycle monitoring service, through the implementation of an awareness system specifically targeted to coastal areas (preparedness phase) and impact assessment (response phase) in the aftermath of a flood event, playing a fundamental role in the implementation of effective recovery and prevention actions. ECFAS benefits from the Copernicus Emergency Management Service products portfolio, and additionally from the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS), the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), and the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (CLMS). Besides, ECFAS capitalises on other publicly available datasets and information derived from past and ongoing initiatives and relevant FP7 and H2020 EU Projects. The technical operational feasibility of the products will be demonstrated through the implementation of the full operational chain, from the forecasting to the impact assessment component. The Technology Readiness Level for a full Copernicus operational deployment in the future at the Pan-EU level will be evaluated, as well as the feasibility, calendar, and cost benefits of the developed products for inclusion. A Roadmap for the operationalisation of the system will be delivered at the end of the project. The integration of data from different sources will require increased computer resources ensured by the usage of the Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) as core processing and databasing service. Lastly, in order to improve and strengthen the strategies implemented in previous projects, a standardised methodology to collect, analyse, and prioritise the user needs and, successively, identify the service requirements will be defined.

The ECFAS concept is summarised in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1 The ECFAS concept.

1.1.1 Structure

WP1 – Project coordination and management – is devoted to coordination and management of ECFAS and will assure smooth progression and effective achievement of project results, facilitating communication among the partners.

In WP2 – Users’ needs and regulatory framework – users’ requirements will be identified together with the regulatory framework, including relevant international Conventions and EU Directives, throughout the project duration. Users’ engagement will be stimulated by involving the national coordinators of the Copernicus User Forum (CUF), national delegates at the Copernicus EU User Forum, and representatives of the relevant core services (CEMS, CMEMS, CLMS, and C3S) in order to reach a larger audience.

WP3 – Coastal exposure and vulnerability: methodologies and dataset – will identify the available datasets of exposure and vulnerability components of the coastal zone and will select the “optimal” algorithm to extract the Satellite-Derived Shoreline (SDS). The algorithm will be used in WP5 and integrated into the platform in WP6.

WP4 – Hindcast/forecast forcing of total water levels and identification of thresholds – will provide Pan-European hindcasts and up to 5-day forecasts of total water levels (TWL) at the coast, including contributions from tides, waves, storm surges, and steric sea level effects related to ocean circulation and density fields. Different modelling systems will be used to produce TWL. A joint analysis of simulated TWL and past coastal flooding events will allow identifying local thresholds of TWL for which coastal flooding could occur and that will activate coastal flood mapping (WP5).

WP5 – Implementation of the coastal flood awareness system and impact assessment – represents the integration of the products defined in WP3 and WP4 into the operational chain of the awareness system. The

WP5 phases will follow a specific set of activities: (i) identification of test sites; (ii) calibration and validation of the flood model (LISFLOOD-FP) at test sites; (iii) implementation of the “mapping” module of the system on the basis of the products already provided in CEMS; (iv) implementation of the impact assessment on assets, population, etc. including a coast-targeted product; and (v) system performance evaluation in hindcast and forecast mode at the Pan-EU level.

WP6 – Proof-of-Concept of integration into CEMS – is dedicated to the design of the PoC and its integration into existing core services in accordance with the requirements relevant to the needs of the users as defined in WP2. The products of the different phases of the PoC implementation will be operationally tested by users to ensure the sustainability of the development through co-design, co-development, and co-evaluation methodologies.

WP7 – Dissemination and exploitation (visibility, transfer, and shared benefits) – will deal with communication, dissemination, exploitation, and uptake, including IPR’s. It will include the dissemination of the results of the project to different types of audiences: private, institutional, and academic users, and a wide stakeholder audience (comprising industry and policymakers, coastal managers, and disaster risk reduction professionals). It will also deal with the Exploitation Plan to identify the project’s outputs with potential for exploitation and by addressing dissemination issues and strategy.

The WP’s structure and connections are represented in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2 Structure of the project

1.2 Context and objectives of the document

Work Package 2 is fundamental for the proposed coastal flood awareness service and mapping products. It uses existing infrastructure related to potential users at the European level and within CEMS, and advances previous efforts in the collection of user needs.

First, current and potential users of EU coastal awareness services that are already part of the existing European Fora (e.g., CUF and users of CEMS and EFAS) were identified. The Copernicus User Forum is composed of public, private, and academic organisations that aim at developing a joint strategy and fostering the exploitation of Copernicus products. Users’ engagement also involved national CUF delegates and national CUF coordinators in France, Germany, Greece, Italy, and Spain (Task 2.1, Deliverable 2.1 – User inventory and engagement, Armaroli et al., 2021). This strategy allowed a better/larger involvement of relevant audiences.

Copernicus as a user-driven Programme centralises the users in the programme’s design and implementation (European Commission, 2019). Their needs and requirements affect the decisions taken at the top of the value chain, contributing to the development of tools for data production. The end-user benefits from a fit-for-purpose service and can provide crucial feedback for the improvement of the overall operational chain. The end-user engagement is useful not only to support building and evaluating final products, but also to identify opportunities for innovation (Schumann et al., 2018), which will take place on ECFAS Roadmap of WP6 (Deliverable 6.4 - Roadmap of ECFAS integration into CEMS).

Building dialogue for the development of relevant Copernicus services is therefore a prerogative of the European Commission, which has introduced a series of interactions to establish a long-term picture of users’ requirements for Copernicus services and satellite configuration. This goal entails the continuous and effective participation of users regarding the definition and validation of service requirements. The Copernicus Regulation¹ in fact specifically mentions the collection of users’ requirements as a cornerstone of the Copernicus evolution, and since then the European Commission has pushed for a consistent and systematic collection of users’ needs in view of the implementation of the programme which include feedback from users but also emerging needs fostered by changes in society, policies and technologies².

The necessity to maintain a continuous dialogue with the users to keep the Copernicus programme relevant and to make it an effective tool for policymaking and policy implementation has been proved in many

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32014R0377>

² https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2019-10/STAFF_WORKING_PAPER_2019-394-Expression_of_User_Needs_for_the_Copernicus_Programme.pdf

contexts. In particular, several studies have assessed user needs for coastal and marine environments, namely (among other):

- An assessment of users’ needs for the definition of an operational coastal service through a case study of Italian institutional users (Geraldini et al., 2021)
- Users’ requirements document for the Sea Level Project of the Climate Change Initiative, including a review and an analysis of the requirements provided within existing documents that come from Global Climate Observing system (GCOS), World Meteorological Organisation (WMO), World Climate Research Program (WCRP), and from the Climate Modelling Group (CMUG). (Legeais et al., 2021)
- An analysis of gaps and recommendations for the evolution of data services for intermediate users at the coastal zone from the Spanish perspective, addressing the need to foster the identification of information lacks for common marine and land applications in coastal areas and promote recommendations for future management (Pérez et al., 2020)
- Users’ requirements for the European Virtual Coastal and Marine Data Warehouse called CoastBase that aims to improve data and information search and exchange. The study discusses users’ requirements and defines relevant and obtainable data and information within the CoastBase project (Eleveld et al., 2003)
- European Flood Awareness System development, where representative organisations, business entities and policy networks were brought on board to identify data gaps and user needs, to ensure that the service and information provided would be useful and relevant³.

The identified users in T2.1, D2.1 – User inventory and engagement (Armaroli et al., 2021) were invited to participate in a survey that aimed at the collection of their technical and operational requirements and needs (Task 2.3 – Collection of users’ requirements). The results are integrated into other WP’s to ensure not only users’ involvement throughout the project lifespan, but also to guarantee the sustainable co-design, co-development, co-evaluation, and co-assessment of the ECFAS front-end platform (WP6).

The present Deliverable 2.3 – Users’ requirement report, which is part of T2.3, is built on a user engagement strategy. Deliverable 2.3 represents the essential requisites of the user pool that will improve and optimise the outputs of ECFAS and increase product efficiency. It aims at fostering the development of value-added downstream services tailored to the requirements and needs of ECFAS end-users. By identifying them, product uptake is easier and adds value to downstream applications (e.g., coastal flood and TWL forecasting, impact assessment, etc.). The results of the Task 2.2 – Policies and Regulations (the analytical overview of the international/EU policy and legal frameworks related to coastal floods) presented in Deliverable 2.2 –

³ <https://climate.copernicus.eu/pluvial-flood-risk-assessment-urban-areas>

Coastal climate resilience: review of policies and regulations (Velegrakis et al., 2021), have been used to identify/classify legal requirements which are also used to tune the ECFAS products and tools.

Therefore, T2.3 major objective is to engage end-users and consider placing their requirements in the design process of the proposed system. More specially, T2.3 aims are: 1) to assess user requirements and needs related to operational/technical specifications in relation to a coastal flood awareness system and mapping products and consider them in the implementation of products/tools of ECFAS; 2) to collect users’ evaluations of the PoC (supporting WP6 Task 6.4 ECFAS – PoC co-evaluation and Roadmap of integration within CEMS); and 3) to assess user requirements together with specifications/coverage of existing EU EWS and the relevant EU policy imperatives and legal obligations, in order to assist in the development of an effective Roadmap for the ECFAS products (WP6 Task 6.4 ECFAS – PoC co-evaluation and Roadmap of integration within CEMS).

Specific actions in the present Deliverable are related to: 1) amending of the pool of potential end-users collated in T2.1 (D2. 1 – User inventory and engagement, Armaroli et al., 2021), and the design and dissemination of a web-based questionnaire among them; 2) the development of a dataset of qualitative and quantitative data of the responses; 3) relevant statistical analyses on this information; and 4) the interpretation of the results, in order to identify and investigate the technical and operational requirements and needs expressed by the interviewed ECFAS potential end-users.

Users’ involvement and requirements support other WP’s (Figure 1.2) and guarantee a two-way process, and their integration into the products being developed. Therefore, T2.3, the collection of users’ requirements:

- validates WP3 in the decision about coastal datasets, including the exposure and vulnerability layers, and the mapping products supporting coastal erosion assessments using satellite-derived shorelines;
- guides WP4 in relation to the selection of the spatial-temporal total water level forecasts and time-frequency updates, and for the return periods of water levels;
- supports WP5 in the selection of the spatial resolution of the coastal flood model, impact and flood maps catalogue characteristics and resolution, and of additional products (e.g., the post-disaster coastal erosion risk assessment);
- informs WP6 in the co-development phase of the ECFAS PoC front-end on the user requirements/preferences as well, as in its co-evaluation stage to optimise and increase exploitation, user uptake, and the value of the evaluation;
- supports WP7 in the strengthening and expansion of the relationships created with end-users ensuring there is a steady flow of information between the project consortium and the end-users.

It is noted that requirements and needs defined by the end-users which due to technical limitations cannot be implemented in the system under development will be considered in the Roadmap of ECFAS integration into CEMS and its delineation with the Copernicus Programme (WP6 T6.4 – ECFAS PoC co-evaluation and

Roadmap of integration within CEMS). The delineation of the Copernicus Programme envisages the evolution of Copernicus products (European Court of Auditors, 2021), therefore the delineation plan between ECFAS and the Copernicus Programme will define the integration of ECFAS as a new product in the Copernicus Core Services.

1.3 Approach

Deliverable 2.3 follows the initial compilation of potential ECFAS end-users presented in D2.1 – User inventory and engagement (Armaroli et al., 2021). It includes the design of a GDPR compliant questionnaire with the involvement of all ECFAS partners, which was eventually activated on LimeSurvey, a platform that enables users to develop and publish surveys from a web-interface, and disseminated among the end-users identified in D2.1. Efforts were made to increase the sample size and representativeness by spreading an external link to the questionnaire and relying on the support of the consortium members, External Board Member (USB and CSET), Work Package 7 via ECFAS social media, and a few online events.

The data were statistically treated and the results obtained are presented and discussed in this report. Some results were publicly discussed during the Second ECFAS Webinar⁴. The scope of the Second ECFAS Webinar was to showcase to the user pool and to new potential ECFAS end-users the results obtained during the first year of the project. This dissemination strategy, supported by WP7, was not only important for the communication of results but also to keep alive the users’ engagement and participation in the development of ECFAS products and the investment in their efficiency and uptake.

1.4 Outline of the document

Deliverable 2.3 – Users’ requirement report has the following outline: Section 2 describes the methodological approach of the questionnaire survey. Section 3 presents the results of the survey. Section 4 discusses and concludes the outcomes of the present work. There are also two Annexes: Annexes A and B that present the questionnaire and the results of the questionnaire survey, respectively.

⁴ <https://www.ecfas.eu/events/2nd-ecfas-webinar>

2 Methods

The collection and analysis of the user needs and requirements was based on: 1) a user involvement process, i.e., using the pool of potential ECFAS users collated in D2.1 - User inventory and engagement (Armaroli et al., 2021) and expanded through continued efforts by the consortium members, the External Board Members (USB and CSET), and the ECFAS social media and online events (Work Package 7); 2) the design of a GDPR compliant questionnaire, structured in seven sections that follow the general framework of ECFAS; 3) questionnaire dissemination through the LimeSurvey platform to the expanded pool of the potential users; and 4) collation and analysis of the questionnaire responses.

2.1 User involvement process: engagement and sampling

Engagement of the potential end-users involved efforts by facilitators and dissemination through ECFAS communication channels. The facilitators were: 1) Project partners and their respective networks; 2) the ECFAS advisory board – the Users Board (Copernicus User Fora Representatives) and the Copernicus Core Services Exploitation Team; 3) CEMS EFAS users, and 4) CMEMS and CLMS users.

During the first period of time, between March and July 2021, the facilitators engaged members of their networks who were considered to be target end-users of ECFAS. ECFAS dissemination continued through a webinar event in May 2021⁵ leading to new registrations to the initial user pool, which finally listed 163 potential users (see also D2.1).

The engagement strategy continued during a second time period, until January 2022. The objective was to increase the size and representativeness of the sample (i.e., the pool of potential end-users). That strategy was based on continuous efforts by the ECFAS partners who disseminated invitations for end-user involvement and links to the ECFAS questionnaire (see Section 2.2 below) to their networks, through social media channels, primarily LinkedIn and Facebook, professional mailing lists as well as topic-related events such as the Copernicus Emergency Management Services Week 2021⁶

The dissemination channels were chosen in order to get perspectives from different communities – covering the whole European territory – within the coastal risk assessment and management field including users of Copernicus services, government agencies (e.g., civil protection agencies), as well as other users of climate and meteorological data. These efforts resulted in the expansion of the initial pool of the ECFAS potential users reported in D2.1, with the final user pool (sample) being composed of 189 people.

⁵ <https://www.ecfas.eu/events/1st-ecfas-webinar/>

⁶ <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/ems/cems-week-2021>

Here it should be mentioned that the geographical distribution of the potential users in the ECFAS pool, reflects also to a large degree the geographical distribution of the ECFAS partners and their networks, i.e., there is an overrepresentation of potential users from the Southern and Mediterranean countries, despite following efforts to expand the pool of potential users from the rest of Europe. This characterises a non-probability (non-random) sampling, i.e., the initial members being recruited are reachable/available in a convenient manner. Non-probability sampling may lead to some members of the population having increased chances of being selected compared to the rest of the population (e.g., in this case certain European countries, and certain work sectors). Nevertheless, non-probability sampling is useful in obtaining opinions and in formulating tentative hypotheses that can be tested more rigorously in further research (Kempf, 2005).

2.2 Questionnaire design and data collection

A web-based anonymous questionnaire was the survey instrument to acquire data about ECFAS potential end-users. It was implemented with LimeSurvey⁷, an open-source internet survey tool. The survey remained active from August 2021 to January 2022.

The design of the questionnaire was primarily centred on its main goal: to determine potential ECFAS end-users’ profile and their needs and requirements in the development and products of the ECFAS awareness system. Nevertheless, the questionnaire also contained questions/options on user requirements, which although will not form part of the current ECFAS tools/products (because they are not foreseen in the ECFAS Description of Action, or due to the availability of data with sufficient resolution at the EU level), can form a basis to inform the Roadmap (Work Package 6, Deliverable 6.4 – Roadmap of ECFAS integration into CEMS) and future improvements of the system. These may include: options for higher spatial resolution and low probability events (e.g., 100-, 500-year return periods), additional coastal risks such as by the wave runup component, and impact assessment of heritage sites. The questionnaire was designed in the framework of WP2 and then discussed with the other WP leaders and amended accordingly. It was also sent to the EBM to collect their feedback.

Generally, the design/development of the ECFAS questionnaire was based on:

- a “top-down” review of the current practices of International, European and national policies and legislation, the existing national coastal flooding early warning systems, and existing user requirements (identified through the EFAS and Copernicus User Fora);
- a “bottom-up” identification of users’ needs and requirements that may have particular significance in the co-design and co-development of ECFAS. These requirements included both operational and technical

⁷ https://manual.limesurvey.org/LimeSurvey_Manual

aspects such as spatial resolution, timelines, type/format of output and layers, the early warning protocols, attitudes to uncertainty/errors, and experiences with similar models/services.

The questionnaire consisted of a total of 38 questions (mandatory and non-mandatory) structured in seven sections that follow the general framework of ECFAS (Annex A): A) stakeholder profile screening; B) coastal awareness system characteristics; C) ECFAS warning components; D) coastal exposure and vulnerability assessment; E) ECFAS mapping products; F) relevant policy and legislation; and G) the ECFAS platform and concluding comments. Special care was given for the questions to be valid, reliable, and easily comprehended. For this reason, each section included an introductory text, to explain the main aim of each section, and each question included specific indications to facilitate their comprehension by the respondents. The questionnaire featured a mix of open- and close-ended questions; the latter allowing for respondents to enlist their comments in detail.

A series of invitation emails introducing the ECFAS project and its rationale, and inviting end-users to participate were sent to the expanded user pool. An external link was also created allowing access to the questionnaire to potential end-users who were not present in the user pool; this external access link was also useful for increasing and diversifying the sample.

To boost the response rate, a series of follow-up reminder invitations to non-respondents were sent every fortnight throughout the period the questionnaire was activated. The option to “opt-out” from the mailing list was always made available. Finally, 62% of the questioned potential end users started and completed the questionnaire, which corresponds to 117 complete responses.

It should be noted that the data protection message was written in compliance with the EU Directive 95/46/EC and the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) enforcing principles of data quality and lawful personal data processing. Each respondent was requested to accept the privacy note before proceeding with the compilation of the anonymous questionnaire.

2.3 Data management, statistical analyses and data quality control

2.3.1 Data management and statistical analyses

Data management was initially carried out in a spreadsheet and then developed in Stata/BE 17.0.

First, the 38 survey questions were organised and transformed into 157 initial variables, both qualitative variables (binary, nominal, and ordinal) and quantitative variables. The raw dataset, composed of the responses from the survey in text data format, was coded in a spreadsheet in standardised codes. The coded dataset was then imported into Stata, where an executable program was developed to manage and analyse the dataset.

Secondly, each pre-existing variable was re-generated in order to give it a new and objective label to facilitate statistical analysis in Stata. New variables were generated, envisaging analyses of demand when some subgroups were too small to be analysed separately – a problem that could be solved by creating new versions of the variables that combine several small categories. The final dataset comprised 337 variables.

New variables were generated by grouping similar ones into clusters, i.e., cluster variables were used to group variables in clusters sharing common characteristics. Clustering allows the reduction of the number of variables for analysis – so these are more easily understood and processed – especially when variables are related to a low number of observations, which has been the case with several initial variables. Therefore, clustering variables with similar characteristics increases the number of observations, the analyses that can be performed, and improves the description of the respondents. The new variables are:

1. Type of organisation (Question 2, Annex A): this question originally listed 15 types of organisations that were clustered into 4 groups. These new groups are: public organisation (national authority, regional authority, environmental protection agency, civil protection, municipality, EU agency or research centre, and international agency); private organisation (private company/SME, large enterprise, private citizen, and EU directorate); academic organisation (university and research institute); and other (international organisation and NGO/association).

2. Country (Question 3, Annex A): the sample is composed of countries worldwide, and they were clustered according to a broad geographical region. As this study was performed for a Pan-European service, it was thought to be necessary to differentiate the European users (Matevosyan et. al., 2017). The cluster and the countries considered in them are: Southern and Mediterranean European Countries (Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Malta, Slovenia, Croatia, Greece and Cyprus), Northern European countries and the UK (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Switzerland, and the UK), and other (Brazil, India, Iraq, Malaysia, Morocco, Peru, and Tunisia).

3. Users of CEMS and EFAS (Questions 7 and 8, Annex A) gave as response options “Yes”, “No”, and “I do not know this service”. Because “I do not know this service” implies the respondent is “not” a user of either of the services, both “No” and “I do not know this service” were clustered into “No”. Therefore, for both questions “Are you a current user of CEMS?” and “Are you a current user of EFAS?” the collected data were treated as “Yes” and “No”, and as such, were also used for statistical analyses.

4. 10-point Likert Scale questions (Questions 6, 17, 22, 26, 28, 29, 31, and 35, Annex A): the 10-point Likert Scale was reset to a 1-5 scale. Therefore, marks 1-2 were grouped as 1, marks 3-4 as 2, marks 5-6 as 3, marks 7-8 as 4, and marks 9-10 as 5. Some of the subgroups (marks from 1 to 10) obtained small numbers of observations. Clustering allows reducing the number of variables for analysis, especially when variables have a low number of observations. Thus, clustering the original 1-10 scale into a 1-5 scale improved the number

of observations in options now corresponding to two extremes and a neutral option linked to the middle answer options.

5. Completion time is a variable automatically registered (in seconds) and included in the dataset by the LimeSurvey tool at the end of each completed questionnaire. This variable proved to be essential for data quality assurance (see Section 2.3.2). Therefore, from the pre-existing variable completion time a new one was created by cutting completion time into ranges of segments. Considering that the minimum completion time was 3 minutes and the maximum 11 hours, for analyses purposes completion time was cut to 15 minutes, 30 minutes, 45 minutes, 60 minutes, 75 minutes, and 11 hours.

The analyses performed were mostly univariate analyses whose objective was to summarise the data to describe the users and their opinions, and find patterns in a cohort. Although the questionnaire was designed to provide information for the development of ECFAS services and products and descriptive statistics were sufficient for this purpose, multivariable analyses were also performed to identify relevant causes or relationships among the responses. This exercise showed no significant association among the majority of the variables tested, which is believed to be related to the characteristics of the sample.

2.3.2 Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity Analysis (SA) can be defined as a series of analyses of a dataset to assess whether altering any of the assumptions made leads to different final interpretations or conclusions (Daniels and Hogan, 2008); it plays a crucial role in assessing the robustness of the findings or conclusions. Despite being often pre-specified in study protocols, many issues suitable for SA are only identified during the review process where peculiarities may emerge (Deeks et al., 2017).

The questionnaire was composed of 38 questions which were often characterised by highly detailed information. The completion time showed a very large range (minimum completion time = 3 minutes, maximum completion time = 11 hours, mean = 52 minutes, SD = 97 minutes, median = 21 minutes). The 15 minutes completion time that corresponds to less than 25 seconds assigned to respond to each question was considered a very short completion time given the nature of the questionnaire and after testing the completion time of ECFAS partners who were aware of the questionnaire content and familiar with the ECFAS terminology. Therefore, completion time (15 minutes) was chosen as the SA eligibility criterion to test if the responses provided below this threshold should be filtered out to guarantee the validity and reliability of the data collected. Considering the whole sample ($n = 117$), 34 respondents completed the survey in less than 15 minutes.

Hence, sensitivity analyses were performed on the basis of the comparisons of the responses between the two populations (i.e., those with completion times above 15 min and the whole sample) considering some central, relevant questions of the questionnaire. The arbitrarily identified as relevant questions cover

fundamental aspects of the ECFAS system: respondents’ interest to test it, ECFAS warning components (TWL), modelled flood extent, and legal framework (familiarity with the EU Floods Directive).

The response frequency of these central questions was verified by: 1) considering the whole sample (n = 117); and 2) considering the sample without the respondents who completed the questionnaire in less than 15 minutes (n = 83). Table 2.1, Table 2.2, Table 2.3, and Table 2.4 show the obtained results.

Table 2.1 Sensitivity analysis for “Are you interested to test ECFAS system at sites of your interest?”.

Interest in testing ECFAS	n (%)
All respondents (n = 117)	96 (82.1)
Removal of respondents (n = 83)	72 (86.7)

Table 2.2 Sensitivity analysis for “What is the minimum acceptable forecast lead time (in days) for total water level for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?”.

Minimum forecast lead time (in days) for TWL	1, n (%)	2, n (%)	3, n (%)	5, n (%)	10, n (%)	30, n (%)
All respondents (n = 117)	22 (18.8)	17 (14.5)	42 (35.9)	25 (21.4)	5 (4.3)	6 (5.1)
Removal of respondents (n = 83)	16 (19.3)	11 (13.3)	32 (38.5)	17 (20.5)	3 (3.6)	4 (4.8)

Table 2.3 Sensitivity analysis for “What type of mapping products are more important for you? - Modelled flood extent”. (Rating 1 – unimportant, 2 – somewhat unimportant, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat important, 5 - very important).

Importance of modelled flood extent as an ECFAS mapping product	1, n (%)	2, n (%)	3, n (%)	4, n (%)	5, n (%)
All respondents (n = 117)	0 (0)	3 (2.5)	14 (12)	33 (28.2)	67 (57.3)
Removal of respondents (n = 83)	0 (0)	2 (2.4)	8 (9.6)	23 (27.7)	50 (60.3)

Table 2.4 Sensitivity analysis for “How familiar are you with the EU Floods Directive?”. (Rating 1 – unfamiliar, 2 – somewhat unfamiliar, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat familiar, 5 – very familiar).

Familiarity with the EU Floods Directive	1, n (%)	2, n (%)	3, n (%)	4, n (%)	5, n (%)
All respondents (n = 117)	22 (18.8)	15 (12.8)	24 (20.5)	23 (19.7)	33 (28.2)
Removal of respondents (n = 83)	16 (19.3)	10 (12)	16 (19.3)	16 (19.3)	25 (30.1)

After performing the SA the findings are very consistent with those from the primary analysis and lead to similar conclusions. Therefore, despite some respondents completing the survey in what was believed to be a very short time, the results based on all the obtained answers can be now regarded with a higher degree of certainty.

3 Results

3.1 ECFAS potential end-users’ profile

A total of 117 responses were collected out of a sample of 189 people who composed the ECFAS user pool, which represents a 62% response rate.

The types of organisations (Question 2, Annex A) were clustered into 4 work sectors: public, private, academic, and other. A high percentage of the respondents work at organisations from the public sector (n = 54, 46.1%), followed by the academic sector (n = 38, 32.5%), private sector (n = 18, 15.4%), and other (n = 7, 6%). The full list of organisations and the clusters they were grouped in is presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Organisations clustered per type of organisation. (n = 117)

Type of organisation	Organisation	n (%)
Public (n = 54)	National authority	30 (55.5)
	Regional authority	11 (20.4)
	Environmental protection agency	4 (7.4)
	Civil protection	7 (13)
	EU research centre	2 (3.7)
Private (n = 18)	Private company/SME	13 (72.1)
	Large enterprise	3 (16.7)
	Private citizen	1 (5.6)
	EU directorate	1 (5.6)
Academic (n = 38)	University	16 (42.1)
	Research institute	22 (57.9)
Other (n = 7)	International organisation	3 (42.9)
	NGO	4 (57.1)

Stata *tabulate* (tab) command summarises a specific variable into frequency tables. Table 3.2 is a one-way frequency table which reports the number of observations (n), relative frequency (%), and cumulative frequency (%) of the variable administrative level of the organisation. The cumulative frequency (%) is the frequency of the first class added to the frequency of the second class and so on.

Table 3.2 Distribution of the geographical level respondents work at and respective cumulative frequencies. (n = 117)

Administrative level	n (%)	Cumulative frequency (%)
Municipal	2 (1.7)	1.7
Regional	29 (24.8)	26.5
National	49 (41.9)	68.4
Pan-European	5 (4.3)	72.7
International	32 (27.3)	100

A high percentage of respondents work at the national level, and the majority perform their work maximum at the national level (cumulative frequency = 68.4%, i.e., the sum of the relative frequencies of the Municipal, Regional, and National level) (Table 3.2).

The total number of responses was collected from 25 mentioned countries and Europe (Question 3, Annex B). The majority of the respondents informed that their organisations were based in Southern and Mediterranean European Countries (Italy: n = 27 (23.1%); Spain n = 16 (13.7%); France n = 15 (12.8%); Greece n = 13 (11.1%); Portugal n = 4 (3.4%); Cyprus n = 2 (1.7%); Malta n = 2 (1.7%); Croatia n = 1 (0.8%); and Slovenia n = 1 (0.8%)).

Table 3.3 is a two-way frequency table which represents the relationship between two sets of categorical data – geographical regions and administrative level of the organisation. Considering the distribution of respondents per geographical location and administrative level of their organisations, the relative frequencies show that the majority is based in Southern and Mediterranean European Countries and most of the work/projects are exploited and utilised within a national scope (cumulative frequency = 72.8%, i.e., the sum of the relative frequencies of respondents working at organisations at Municipal, Regional, and National levels within Southern and Mediterranean regions of Europe) (Table 3.3). By comparison, respondents based in Northern European Countries and the UK appear to have been active also at the international level, in addition to the national level (Table 3.3).

Table 3.3 Distribution of respondents per geographical region and administrative level of their organisations. (n = 117)

Geographical regions	Administrative level n (%)				
	Municipal	Regional	National	Pan-EU	International
Southern and Mediterranean EU Countries	2 (2.5)	26 (32)	31 (38.3)	3 (3.7)	19 (23.5)
Northern EU Countries and UK	0 (0)	2 (6.7)	15 (50)	2 (6.7)	11 (36.6)
Other	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	3 (50)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)

This respondent distribution, could be explained by the geographical distribution of the ECFAS consortium members, who had a prominent role in the Questionnaire dissemination.

The respondents were asked about the natural hazards they mainly deal with at their organisations intending to relate their interests to the hazards being addressed by ECFAS. Among the 18 hazard types provided (Table 3.4), coastal flooding, coastal erosion, storm surge, and river flooding are the most relevant for the end-users.

Table 3.4 Multiple choice question asking the type of natural hazards the respondents mainly deal with. (n = 117)

Types of natural hazards	n (%)
Coastal flooding	91 (77.8)
Coastal erosion	81 (69.2)
Storm surge	66 (56.4)
River flooding	61 (52.1)
Heavy precipitations	52 (44.4)
Marine storms	49 (41.9)
Flash-floods	47 (40.2)
Landslides	40 (34.2)
Droughts	34 (29.1)
Windstorms	29 (24.8)
Tsunamis	27 (23.1)
Earthquakes	27 (23.1)
Forest fires	26 (22.2)
Heatwaves	23 (19.7)
Tropical cyclones	22 (18.8)
Wildfires	17 (14.5)
Volcanic activity	16 (13.7)
Cold spells	12 (10.3)
Other	6 (5.1)

Since ECFAS builds upon the framework of EFAS and aims at contributing to the evolution of CEMS, it is important to gauge the end-users’ knowledge about these services. The majority of the respondents are not users either of CEMS (n = 64, 54.7%) or of EFAS (n = 93, 79.5%) (Questions 7 and 8, Annex B).

Considering exclusively the respondents that deal with river flooding and with flash-floods (Table 3.4) — both hydrological natural hazards that are within the scope of EFAS — the majority are not users of the European Flood Awareness System; surprisingly almost 70% of the respondents dealing with river flooding flash-floods are not users of EFAS

The CEMS services also seem not to be widely used among the respondents from public organisations (Table 3.5), which also includes civil protection agencies, although these users are expected to be the main CEMS target group. On the other hand, the majority of the respondents in the user pool who work at private organisations appear to be users of CEMS (Table 3.5).

Table 3.5 Distribution of users of CEMS per type of organisation. (n = 53)

Users of CEMS per type of organisation	n (%)
Public	27 (50)
Private	12 (66.7)
Academic	12 (31.6)
Other	2 (28.6)

3.2 Usage and limitations of currently available coastal awareness systems

The questionnaire also sought to obtain information on the usage and limitations of currently available awareness systems (Questionnaire Section B, Annex A). The results show that the majority of the respondents (70%) do not currently use an awareness system (Question 9, Annex B).

The 35 respondents (30%) who answered positively to Question 9 were asked to provide information on the service provider (Question 10, Annex B). Most declared that they use a service developed within their organisation, followed by those using national and regional government services. Interestingly, there has been a lonely respondent declaring the use of a European public service, which suggests that there is a large scope for the development and dissemination of such a service. In addition, it appears that the services used by the respondents do not provide in most cases evaluation of the impacts on the coastal area (Question 11, Annex B); less than a third of the respondents using coastal awareness services declared the availability of information on impact evaluation.

The questionnaire also tried to obtain more detailed information on the different elements of the coastal awareness services used (Question 12, Annex B). The question offered multiple options as well as it allowed for the respondents to declare additional elements. The responses, shown in Figure 3.1, suggest that most services are associated with hydrodynamic forecasts, followed by exposure and vulnerability information. Impact assessment and flood maps elements do not appear to be readily available in most cases.

Figure 3.1 Elements present in the coastal awareness/early warning system. (n = 35) Note: numbers represent all answers provided (multiple option question)

The questionnaire survey intended to give the opportunity to the respondents to list the major limitations and suggest improvements in the coastal awareness services currently used by them. Interesting insights and several limitations of the services were listed (Question 13, Annex B). These include limitations on the spatial extent and accuracy, the provision of flooded area forecasts (flood extent, intensity, and depth) and post-impact assessments, forecast evaluation, as well as a lack of operational mapping and coastal risk mapping.

The respondents also declared that there is a lack of information on past extreme event characteristics (e.g., met-ocean forcing conditions, post-event model re-analysis, impacted areas, damages), and forecast driven impact assessments, as well as computational power limitations. They also suggested improvements related, for example, to: the translation of operational marine weather forecasts to coastal impacts (flooding and erosion), the data update cycle and the flood forecast accuracy. Most of the above limitations and suggested improvements are addressed in the ECFAS tools and products (Work Packages 4, 5, and 6).

When the potential users were asked on the importance of a Pan-European Coastal Flood Awareness System for their organisation (Question 14, Annex B), the large majority (78.6%) answered that such a system would be somewhat important or important. They also chose their preferred activities that such a system could facilitate (Question 15, Annex B), which are shown in Figure 3.2. The activities topping the list were related to the impact assessment on the built environment, coastal exposure evaluations, provision of coastal flood maps, impact assessments on coastal populations and the analysis of the evolution of the coastline. Many of these activities will be facilitated by the ECFAS platform and products.

Figure 3.2 Preferred activities that a coastal awareness system could facilitate. (n = 117) Note: numbers represent all answers provided (multiple option question).

3.3 ECFAS operational and technical specifications required by the potential end-users

3.3.1 Hydrodynamic warning components

ECFAS will provide information on coastal total water level (TWL), which integrates mean sea level, tidal level, and storm surge level (SSL), and the wave setup components. Therefore, the questionnaire intended to investigate the importance end-users give to TWL, SSL, and wave characteristics, and their needs and requirements concerning the technical specifications of those components. It should be noted that the questionnaire included an option for wave runup forecast, although due to lack of Pan-EU datasets and

information with a sufficient accuracy for its estimation, this has not been included in the ECFAS products; the option was included to gauge the interest of the potential end-users for such a product.

The respondents were asked about the importance of TWL, SSL, wave characteristics, and wave runup for the performance of their work (Figure 3.3). All components were considered somewhat important or very important by at least 65% of the respondents, with the TWL topping the preference list.

Figure 3.3 Importance of each warning component for the respondents’ work. Rating 1 – unimportant, 2 – somewhat unimportant, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat important, 5 – very important, N/A = unknown terminology. (n = 117)

Respondents were introduced to the technical characteristics of the hydrodynamic warning components that will be used in ECFAS (TWL, SSL, and wave climate), as well as wave runup – spatial resolution (m), update frequency (hrs), and forecast lead time (days) – and they were asked to choose their preferred technical specification. Schumann et al. (2018) highlight the importance of product attributes that are important for users and that include technical specifications like timeliness and resolution of the data.

Regarding spatial resolution, the preferred option for all warning components was 100 m, the finest resolution listed (Question 18, Annex B). Approximately 50% of the respondents chose that resolution for TWL and wave runup, whereas 30% selected that option for SSL and wave climate.

Respondents clearly opt for an update frequency of TWL, SSL, and wave runup every 6 hrs (Question 20, Annex B). On the other hand, the wave climate update frequency showed similar results for 24, 12, and 6 hrs. Lastly, the forecast lead time selected by the respondents for all the discussed components was 3 days. Percentages vary from 35.9% (TWL) to 31.6% (wave runup) (Question 21, Annex B).

Storm event’s return period, or storm events’ probability, was also an investigated topic. Return periods are essential parameters in the architecture of ECFAS as they define water levels that will exceed the forecasted TWL thresholds, and trigger the warning component of the system.

The respondents were asked to evaluate the importance of the following storm events for their work: 1-, 5-, 10-, 50-, 100-, and 500-year return period (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4 Importance of storm events probability according to the respondents. N/A = unknown terminology. (n = 117)

Most of the respondents consider the 10-, 50-, and 100-year return period events as very important (53.8%, 53.8%, and 54.7%, respectively). Similarly, the 1-, 5-, and 500-year return period events are also considered very important (42.7%, 45.3%, and 36.7%, respectively).

These findings suggest that the majority of the end-users are interested in medium probability events (10-, 50-, and 100-year return periods). However, events corresponding to a higher probability of occurrence (1- and 5-year return periods), thus potentially triggering the ECFAS warning system at a higher frequency, are also very important to a high percentage of the sample.

Question 23 (Annex B) was a non-mandatory open question where the respondent could inform if there was any other event probability of interest for their work purposes. Of 9 received answers, the most frequently mentioned events were those with 2-, 20-, 200-, 250-, and 1,000-year return periods.

Work Package 4 Deliverable 4.3 (Report on the identification of local thresholds of TWL for triggering coastal flooding) reports on the Extreme Value Analysis implemented to estimate TWL’s for return periods (1 – 50 years) that were used as reference for the selection of the triggering threshold for the activation of the warning system and the design of the flood map catalogue (Deliverable 5.4 – Pan-EU flood maps catalogue).

The triggering thresholds are based on the 1-year return period TWL. Return periods from 2 to 50 years were used for the definition of TWL extreme scenarios (D5.4 technical document). The selection of those return periods addresses respondents’ preferences.

3.3.2 Coastal flood mapping and exposure and vulnerability assessment

The ECFAS warning component is based on the provided thresholds of TWL that can trigger the retrieval of reference coastal flood maps that are part of a Pan-EU flood map catalogue for coastal flood prone areas (Deliverable 5.4 – Pan-EU flood maps catalogue).

70% of the respondents consider flood maps a very important product for their work purposes (Figure 3.3). Concerning technical specifications, one third of the respondents opted for maps with fine spatial resolution (Table 3.6). The options 100- and 50-m spatial resolutions showed similar relative frequencies (23.1% and 21.4%, respectively).

The flood maps catalogue (Deliverable 5.4) will include Pan-European coastal flood maps extension, water depth and velocity with a resolution of 100 m, produced in the framework of Work Package 5 Task 5.4 Modelling of coastal flood characteristics along flood-prone areas at EU level. The decision to use a resolution of 100 m was taken considering both the outcomes of the users’ consultation (the questionnaire survey) and the analyses carried out to validate the flood model LISFLOOD-FP (Deliverable 5.2 - Validated LISFLOOD-FP model for coastal areas, Le Gal et al. 2021). A resolution of 100 m was the best compromise taking into account the results of the testing, the computational demand, and the users’ requirements

Table 3.6 Spatial resolution (in metres) for coastal flood maps selected by the respondents. (n = 117)

Spatial resolution (m)	n (%)
25	39 (33.3)
50	25 (21.4)
100	27 (23.1)
300	6 (5.1)
500	11 (9.4)
1,000	7 (6)
3,000	0 (0)
5,000	2 (1.7)

Regarding the other technical specifications — time frequency update (in hours) and forecast lead time (in days) – the flood map component follows the same response pattern as the hydrodynamic warning components that will be part of ECFAS system (TWL, SSL, wave climate). Respondents indicated a 6-hr minimum time frequency update (Question 20, Annex B) and a 3-day minimum forecast lead time (Question 21, Annex B). The TWL forecast lead time in ECFAS is up to 5 days, with the best performance achieved for

the 3-day forecasts (Deliverable 4.1 - Report on the calibration and validation of hindcasts and forecasts of TWL); therefore, ECFAS will meet the requirements of the users in relation to the forecast lead time.

The impact assessment component is part of ECFAS system’s architecture (Questionnaire Section D, Annex A) and a target activity in Work Package 5. In Work Package 3 Deliverable 3.1 — Coastal dataset including exposure and vulnerability layers (Ieronymidi and Grigoriadis, 2021) constitutes an inventory of datasets for exposure and vulnerability analysis of coastal areas; this dataset lists products that provided the ground for the impact assessment carried out within the framework of WP5.

Question 25 (Annex B) elucidates that 53% of the sample (n = 62) evaluate exposure and/or vulnerability. Based on the responses from those 62 respondents, Question 26 (Annex B) intended to examine the importance given to the following elements in the evaluation of exposure and vulnerability for impact assessment: population, buildings, infrastructure and transport networks, utility networks, commercial and industrial activities, cultural heritage, ecosystems, and agriculture. Apart from the latter, all elements have been indicated in the responses as very important for impact assessment (Figure 3.5). The most important elements indicated by the respondents are: population, buildings, infrastructure and transport networks. Population and asset elements are important for WP5 to develop coastal flooding impact assessments for the flood maps included in the flood catalogue (Deliverable 5.4 - Pan-EU flood maps catalogue) which will include also the impact catalogue. As a matter of fact, cultural heritage is the only element not currently being considered in the impact assessment component of ECFAS.

Figure 3.5 Importance of elements to evaluate exposure and vulnerability for impact assessment according to the respondents that evaluate exposure and vulnerability for impact assessment. (n = 62)

The questionnaire also intended to examine how useful it would be to conduct a social vulnerability assessment for coastal flood risk reduction (Question 27, Annex B). Social vulnerability refers to the characteristics of a group in terms of their capacity to anticipate, cope with, resist, and recover from the impact of a natural hazard. Social vulnerability indices assess the potential of the pre-event inherent characteristics of a society that could aggravate physical loss. 75.2% of the respondents (n = 88) consider such an assessment would be at least somewhat useful.

3.4 Importance of ECFAS mapping products to the potential end-users

ECFAS mapping products will include a set of layers related to coastal exposure and vulnerability evaluation and risk assessment provided for past events in scenarios of TWL threshold exceedance (Task 5.5 Mapping products). The mapping products will be used to display on the ECFAS platform information of the affected location, such as the observed flood extension, related impact assessment (e.g., impact assessment on assets and population), pre-event shoreline position to improve CEMS mapping products (Joubert-Boitat et al., 2020), and others.

The collaboration with end-users in the process of product development ensures innovation and maximises users’ understanding and application of the products (Schumann et al., 2018). Therefore, the end-user questionnaire intended to examine the importance the users give to several mapping products possibly being developed and delivered by ECFAS.

Amongst a list of 16, the top five mapping products which the majority of the respondents rated as very important are: (1) modelled flood extent; (2) pre- and post-shoreline position detection; (3) event-based coastal flood notifications; (4) identification of hotspots; and (5) detailed damage assessment analysis over affected areas (Question 28, Annex B). These findings validate the mapping products proposed in the architecture of ECFAS. Furthermore, post-disaster coastal erosion risk assessment, which was contemplated as a proposed additional mapping product depending on the users’ requirements, was considered very important by a significant fraction of the user pool (n = 56, 47.9%).

Frequency analysis was performed between the importance respondents attributed to the mapping products and types of organisations (Figure 3.6 and Table 3.7). That allowed to narrow down the survey results to the specific group of responses given by respondents from different types of organisations and examine the difference in their potential products uptake.

Figure 3.6 Distribution of mapping products indicated as very important by respondents from different types of organisations.

The relative frequency indicates that most of the listed mapping products are considered very important mainly to the public sector cohort (Figure 3.6). It is valid to draw attention to those mapping products indicated as very important by at least 50% of the respondents from the public sector: (1) information on relevant meteorological conditions; (2) detailed damage assessment analysis over affected areas; (3) event-based coastal flood notifications; (4) assessment of coastal and marine flood map forecasting skills; (5) impact assessment on population and assets; (6) modelled flood extent; (7) vulnerable population mapping; and (8) geographical information.

The mapping products pre- and post-event beach width dimension and post-event magnitude of beach width change are very important to around 44.5% of the respondents from the academic sector, whereas equally very important to both public and academic sectors is monitoring of temporal evolution of the shoreline position after events (41.1%) (Table 3.7).

Table 3.7 Distribution of mapping products indicated to be very important by respondents from different types of organisations.

Mapping product	Type of organisation			
	Public n (%)	Private n (%)	Academic n (%)	Other n (%)
Pre- and post-event beach width dimension	17 (36.2)	8 (17)	21 (44.7)	1 (2.1)
Post-event magnitude of beach width change	18 (40)	7 (15.6)	20 (44.4)	0 (0)
Monitoring of temporal evolution of the shoreline position after events	23 (41.1)	9 (16)	23 (41.1)	1 (1.8)
Pre- and post-event shoreline position detection	29 (44.6)	10 (15.4)	25 (38.5)	1 (1.5)
Post-event shoreline displacement magnitude	25 (44.6)	8 (14.3)	22 (39.3)	1 (1.8)
Coastal defence structures layer	18 (45)	6 (15)	14 (35)	2 (5)
Post-disaster coastal erosion risk assessment	22 (45.8)	7 (14.6)	17 (35.4)	2 (4.2)
Identification of erosional hot-spots	28 (45.9)	10 (16.4)	21 (34.4)	2 (3.3)
Geographical information	21 (50)	9 (21.4)	10 (23.8)	2 (4.8)
Vulnerable population mapping	30 (53.6)	9 (16.1)	13 (23.2)	4 (7.1)
Modelled flood extent	37 (55.2)	7 (10.4)	20 (29.9)	3 (4.5)
Impact assessment on population and assets	32 (57.1)	7 (12.5)	13 (23.2)	4 (7.1)
Assessment of coastal and marine flood map forecasting skills	33 (57.9)	6 (10.5)	16 (28.1)	2 (3.5)
Event-based coastal flood notifications	36 (59)	7 (11.5)	15 (24.6)	3 (4.9)
Detailed damage assessment analysis over affected areas	35 (59.3)	7 (11.9)	14 (23.7)	3 (5.1)
Information on relevant meteorological conditions	32 (60.4)	8 (15.1)	11 (20.7)	2 (3.8)

Regarding the private sector cohort, the mapping product considered most important is geographical information, indicated by 21.4% of the respondents (Table 3.7). Other mapping products indicated by approximately 16.5% of the respondents from the private sector are: (1) pre- and post-event beach width dimension; (2) identification of erosional hot-spots; (3) vulnerable population mapping; and (4) monitoring of temporal evolution of the shoreline position after events. Other mapping products considered in the question and evaluated by this specific cohort fall below this percentage.

3.5 Coastal flood-related policies and legislation as seen by the potential end-users

The survey provided unexpected results regarding users’ familiarity with international and EU policies and legislation pertinent to coastal areas resilience to flood risk. Respondents declared being unfamiliar-moderately familiar with the existing (and emerging) policies and legislation (Figure 3.7). More than half of the respondents declared to be unfamiliar or somewhat unfamiliar with significant international and EU policies and legislation, such as the EU Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Directive 2014/52/EU (57.3%), the 2015 Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR)⁸ (53%) and the corresponding EU SFDRR Action Plan (55.6%)⁹, the Union Civil Protection Mechanism UCPM¹⁰ (52.1%), and the Public Access to

⁸ https://www.unisdr.org/files/43291_sendaiframeworkfordrren.pdf

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/echo/sites/default/files/sendai_swd_2016_205_0.pdf

¹⁰ Decision (EU) 2019/420 (13/3/2019) on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32019D0420>

Environmental Information Directive (PAEI, 2003/4/EC)¹¹ (51.3%). Given that these form part of the EU policy and legal framework, it should be mentioned that 5.1% (n = 6) of the sample comprise non-Europeans (Brazil, India, Malaysia, Morocco, Peru, Tunisia, and Peru) who are not expected to be familiar with the EU framework. The low familiarity of the respondents with the SFDRR and the EU SFDRR Action Plan is noteworthy, as these set measures/targets for 2030, including for the availability of and access to EWS and disaster risk information and assessments, and promote policies based on research/innovation, the co-design, co-development, co-evaluation, and strengthening of emergency climate services. Similarly, there is low familiarity shown in the responses for the UCPM, which asks the EU Member States to carry out flood risk assessments, the EIA Directive, which requires coastal flood assessments to facilitate coastal infrastructure resilience and environmental protection, and the PAEI, 2003/4/EC.

Figure 3.7 Level of familiarity respondents indicated to each of the policies and legislation relevant to coastal flooding risk. Rating 1 – unfamiliar, 2 – somewhat unfamiliar, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat familiar, 5 – very familiar. (n = 117)

Familiarity level somewhat improved regarding the remainder policy and legislation instruments. The highest familiarity was shown for the 2021 EU Climate Change Adaptation Strategy¹², for which only 21.4% declared to be unfamiliar or somewhat unfamiliar. The Strategy mentions coastal floods and promotes, amongst

¹¹ Directive 2003/4/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 on public access to environmental information and repealing Council Directive 90/313/EEC, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32003L0004>

¹² COM/2013/0216 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=COM:2013:0216:FIN:EN:PDF>

others, improved relevant data availability and usability from EU scientific lighthouses. At the same time, few respondents declared to be very familiar with all considered instruments (Figure 3.7), with only the Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC)¹³ and the INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC)¹⁴ scoring more than 30%. Interestingly, only 28.2% of the respondents declared to be very familiar with the extremely relevant Flood Directive (FD, 2007/60/EC)¹⁵, which, in addition to its relevance, is a mature legal instrument with its second implementation cycle completed. The FD imposes a general duty to the EU Members States to assess the coastal flood risk, map the flood extent, assets, and humans at risk, draw up comprehensive flood hazard and flood risk maps (FHRM’s) and flood risk management plans (FRMP’s) in recurring implementation cycles. Only 12% of the respondents declared to be very familiar with the UCPM, which can be explained by the low representativeness of the civil protection sector in the sample (see also below). Similar rankings were shown for the EU Climate Law (Regulation (EU)2021/1119)¹⁶, which envisages strong action on resilience-building that could benefit by facilitating improved coastal flood risk assessments and management; this might be explained by the short time since its adoption. Also, less than 40% of the respondents declared to be somewhat and very familiar to the 2008 Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) Protocol to the Barcelona Convention¹⁷ which addresses specifically coastal erosion and flooding and their detection/warning (Arts. 8, 23 and 24).

In order to get a better insight into the responses of the potential end-users, frequency analysis was performed between the respondent awareness ratings and their profiles. Due to the relatively small number of respondents (n = 117), significant results could not be found for all cohorts. For example, the low familiarity related to the UCPM can be explained by the low representativeness in the sample of civil protection agencies; when this cohort is analysed alone (n = 7, 6%) most respondents from such agencies (n = 6, 85.7%) declared to be somewhat familiar and very familiar with the UCPM.

Similar patterns were found in the frequency analyses performed between the respondents’ parent organisation (public, private, academic, and other) and their familiarity with policy and legislation. Respondents from public organisations appear to be more familiar with the considered policies and legislation than respondents from private and academic sectors. For instance, analysis of the responses related to the familiarity with the SFDRR, for which 53% were rated as unfamiliar and somewhat familiar

¹³ Directive 2000/60/EC <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000L0060>

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02007L0002-20190626>

¹⁵ Directive 2007/60/EC 23/10/2007 on the assessment and management of flood risks <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32007L0060>

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 30/6/2021 amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R1119&from=EN>

¹⁷ https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/14031/08IG18_Final_Act_iczm_eng.pdf

(Figure 3.7), has found a clear difference between the public, the private, and the academic sectors. Respondents from the public sector rated their awareness (in a 1-5 scale) better ($n = 54$, mean = 2.8, SD = 1.5) than those from the private ($n = 18$, mean = 1.8, SD = 1.1) and the academic sector ($n = 38$, mean = 2.3, SD = 1.4). Analysis of the responses regarding the amended EIA Directive 2014/52/EU, for which 39.3% of the respondents declared to be unfamiliar and only 14.5% very familiar (Figure 3.7), suggests similar patterns; respondents from the public sector rated their familiarity much better ($n = 54$, mean = 2.6, SD = 1.6) than those from the private sector ($n = 18$, mean = 2.3, SD = 1.4), and the academic sector ($n = 38$, mean = 2.0, SD = 1.3).

Notwithstanding their level of familiarity, potential end-users responded favourably with regard to the usefulness of a coastal flood awareness system for the implementation of relevant policies detailed in the 2021 EU CCA Strategy, with more than 77% declaring that such a system would be somewhat useful or very useful (Figure 3.8). Moreover, a large majority of the respondents (77.7%) rated ECFAS as somewhat or extremely useful in contributing to the coastal risk reduction in coastal areas (Question 31, Annex B).

Figure 3.8 Rating of the usefulness of a coastal flood awareness system in the implementation of policies of the 2021 EU CCA Strategy. Rating 1 – irrelevant, 2 – somewhat irrelevant, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat useful, 5 – very useful. ($n = 117$)

The responses to the question of relevance of the ECFAS products to the monitoring the shoreline position (Question 32, Annex B), suggest that such products are quite pertinent: 60.7% of the respondents find them somewhat and extremely useful. These findings are not only important in the context of the coastal policies and legislation, but also appear to verify the preference for such mapping products identified in Section 3.4 (Figure 3.6 and Table 3.7).

3.6 Questionnaire survey concluding questions

In the final section of the questionnaire (Questionnaire Section G, Annex A), the potential end-users were asked questions on the potential utilisation of the coastal flood awareness platform, the usefulness of certain platform attributes (catalogues and archives of products), as well as on their familiarity with geospatial information formats and their preferred communication channels. The answers provided have been very useful and informed the considerations on the ECFAS platform development and communication strategy.

With regard to the ECFAS attributes, the majority of the respondents declared that a catalogue and an archive of the ECFAS products would be extremely useful. 93.2% of respondents have said that a product catalogue would be at least somewhat useful (Question 33, Annex B), whereas the usefulness of a product archive showed similar grading (91.5 % of the respondents find it extremely and somewhat useful) (Question 33, Annex B). These preferences are reflected in the development and products of the ECFAS platform. The ECFAS platform will store forecasted TWL time-series at coastal points and the forecasted coastal flood and impacts in case of an activation. The platform will enable the end-user to go back in time and download coastal flood and impact layers for areas where a warning was issued, or to display and download past forecasted TWL time series. The platform will also make available a list of past events in the satellite-based mapping menu. For further information, refer to Deliverable 6.1 – ECFAS Platform architecture and design document (ECFAS project, 2021), which mentions the storage in the platform and gives a first overview of the aspect of the platform, and to Deliverable 6.2 – ECFAS Platform ready for demonstration activities, which exhibits the final version of the platform and the progress of the integration of the algorithms.

A useful finding is related to the Question 35 (Annex B) related to the respondent knowledge of different formats of geospatial information. Except for GeoPackage (.gpkg) geospatial format, at least 50% of the respondents declared to be somewhat and very knowledgeable of all other format options (Figure 3.9). These findings have been also useful in terms of informing the format choices of the geospatial information adopted in the ECFAS platform.

Figure 3.9 Knowledge level the respondents indicated to have of geospatial information formats. Rating 1 – unknowledgeable, 2 – somewhat unknowledgeable, 3 – moderate, 4 – somewhat knowledgeable, 5 – very knowledgeable (n = 117)

The format of the products implemented in each WP and included in the ECFAS platform can be summarised as follows:

- Work Package 3, Deliverable 3.1 – Coastal dataset including exposure and vulnerability layers (Ieronymidi and Grigoriadis, 2021) refers to the use of vector files (shapefiles – .shp), raster files (GeoTIFF), and CSV. SAET algorithm outputs (Deliverable 3.2 – Algorithms for satellite derived shoreline, Pardo-Pascual et al., 2021) are Shapefiles (.shp) and GeoJSON. WP3 facilitates results in both formats so that they can be used indistinctly in web environments or in Geographic Information Systems.
- Work Package 4 uses NetCDF for the coastal total water level forecasts produced daily in the warning algorithm. The CSV format is also used as it allows the exchange of information between different algorithms (input/output). However, at first it should not be useful for the end-users.
- The output formats of the impact catalogue developed within Work Package 5 are the following: Shapefile (.shp), .tif, CSV, .txt (the final format will depend on the type of impact considered). Still within the framework of WP5, the flood maps will be delivered in Geo TIFF and NetCDF.
- The system’s back-end developed in Work Package 6 will store vector layers in GeoJSON format and raster layers in NetCDF format, whereas for the front-end downloading function, vector layers are in GeoJSON format and raster layers are in GeoTIFF format.

The questionnaire survey also identified how the potential end-users would preferably use a coastal flood awareness platform (Question 36, Annex B). The question offered multiple options as well as it allowed for the respondents to declare other potential uses. The results show that informing was a preferred usage (104), followed by raising awareness (80), and deciding for responses (51). A few respondents (9) opted for other

uses, such as to advise, schedule local actions, complete EFAS, use as boundary conditions for high-resolution flood modelling, plan civil protection responses, for post-event assessments, and for comparisons with their own systems. These results have informed the fine-tuning of the ECFAS platform.

The question related to the users’ motivation to test the ECFAS system at sites of their interest (Question 37. Annex B) indicates that the large majority (82.1%) of the respondents showed interest for testing the platform. This is a very good indication that the ECFAS platform may have a clear pathway towards its eventual adoption by potential end-users.

Finally, the potential end-users were asked on their choices for communication channels to share ECFAS updates (Question 38, Annex B). Similar to Question 36, multiple options were offered. The results show that information dissemination through the ECFAS website (82), e-newsletter (78) and related events (50) are by far the preferred choices. Interestingly, information dissemination through social media platforms was the least preferred option (38). This result may reflect both the nature of the dissemination tasks (i.e., the potential volume and details of the updates), as well as the composition of the respondents (i.e., science and engineering experts). In any case, these findings have been carefully considered and adjusted the ECFAS dissemination strategy adopted throughout the project by Work Package 7.

4 Discussion and concluding remarks

The major objective of Deliverable 2.3 Users’ requirements report is to present the assessed user requirements and needs related to operational/technical specifications of a coastal flood awareness system and associated mapping products, and consider them in the implementation of products/tools of ECFAS. In that sense, the collation of the ECFAS pool (inventory) of 189 potential end-users, and the collection of questionnaire responses from 62% of this user pool represent an extremely important achievement of the ECFAS project, providing important input in the collection of information from users who will potentially exploit and uptake the developed services.

A total of 117 responses were collected out of a sample of 189 potential end-users, which represents a 62% response rate. Response rate is an important aspect for the representativeness of the results; a low rate may induce selection bias as respondents may differ systematically from non-respondents. A 60% response rate is considered adequate, when a survey of a general population aims to describe knowledge or behaviours, although a 70% response rate would be preferable (Roth and BeVier, 1998). In order to reach higher response rates, it is essential the respondents have experience with related questions which must be valid, reliable, and easily comprehended. Besides, response rates increase when a short, prenotification invitation email introduces the coming e-mail survey and provides “opt-in” or “opt-out” options to participate, as well as follow-up reminder e-mails that can spike response rates. (Andrews et al., 2003). Both strategies were closely followed by the ECFAS questionnaire survey. Moreover, previous experiences in this type of questionnaire surveys (climatic hazards and impacts on the natural and human environment) suggest that a 62% response rate of a pool of 189 end-users is very satisfactory (e.g., Asariotis et al., 2018; Geraldini et al., 2021).

Responses were collected from 25 countries, the majority of which came from potential users from Southern and Mediterranean European Countries; most of the respondents based in these countries work within a national scope (national, regional, and municipal levels) (72.8%).

The analysis of the profile of the respondents has shown that a high percentage of them work for public organisations (46.1%). Some important work sector-related groups were found to be under-represented, especially the private sector, the environmental protection agencies, and the civil protection agencies; the latter is an important target group of ECFAS and as such, it would have been preferable to obtain a broader view of their needs and requirements for the uptake and exploitation of ECFAS.

Respondents are mostly interested in natural hazards such as coastal flooding, coastal erosion, storm surge, and river flooding. It should be noted that coastal flooding, storm surges and coastal erosion are hazards that are integrated in the development of ECFAS. Coastal flood and coastal erosion are the core of the mapping

products that ECFAS will deliver, whereas storm surge integrates in the TWL warning component responsible for triggering the flood awareness system.

The vast majority of the respondents are not current users of either CEMS or EFAS. The CEMS services appear not to be widely utilised by users from public and academic organisations, although their users are usually policymakers and public authorities, such as environmental or civil protection agencies. Other users include commercial and private users, the academic and research sectors, and not-for-profit organisations (European Commission, 2017). All these groups are present in the ECFAS user pool. However, considering the present findings, it seems that there is space to promote CEMS and the development of related applications and value-added services and products.

ECFAS will provide information on coastal total water level (i.e., the combined mean sea level, tidal level, storm surge level and wave setup), and the questionnaire investigated the needs and requirements concerning the technical specifications of these components. Respondents consider information on all the above hydrodynamic components of the warning system very important, confirming the relevance of such as system. All these components are integrated in the ECFAS warning system.

It is noteworthy, that the estimation/forecasts concerning the wave runup have been considered as somewhat important and very important by 65 % of the respondents (Figure 3.3). Forecasts for high wave runup (“sneaker waves”) can be very useful in terms of increasing the safety of beach-goers, as well as assessing its potential synergies with the coastal erosion/flooding (e.g., Sheremet et al., 2014; Stockdon et al., 2014; García -Medina et al., 2018). In addition, the wave run up is associated with a very important aspect of the management of coastal zones, as it legally defines the public/private domain boundary in the (autonomous) coastal legislation of several EU Member States (D2.2 Coastal climate resilience: review of policies and regulations, Velegrakis et al., 2021). However, wave runup has not been considered in the development of the ECFAS system, because of the lack of the information needed for its estimation such as the foreshore beach slope and surf zone bathymetry (Holman and Sallenger, 1985; Stockdon et al., 2006; 2014). That information is not available at Pan-EU scale, and at the resolution needed along the EU coastline to provide accurate and reliable results. The results of the questionnaire as well as the significance of the wave runup for the management of coastal zone and its risks suggest that runup-related forecasts and mapping products should be considered in Deliverable 6.4 – Roadmap of ECFAS integration into CEMS.

Regarding the technical characteristics of the ECFAS hydrodynamic warning components (TWL, SSL, and waves), respondents indicated a preference for: 100-m spatial resolution (the best resolution option offered), 6-hour update frequency, and 3-day forecast lead time. These preferences have been taken into consideration and, when feasible, integrated in the system as, for instance, the forecast lead time (WP4).

An important question was associated with the preferences for the return periods of extreme events. Estimation of the return period of extreme (TWL) events are central in the ECFAS tools/products, i.e., for the design of the warning system activation (Deliverable 4.3 – Report on the identification of local thresholds of TWL for triggering coastal flooding) and of the flood map catalogue computing (D5.4 - Pan-EU flood maps catalogue). The findings show that the majority of the end-users are interested in medium probability events (10-, 50-, and 100-year return periods), although events corresponding to a higher probability of occurrence (1- and 5-year return periods), were also considered very important to a high percentage of respondents. These preferences have been mostly taken into consideration for the design of the flood catalogue and of the activation of the warning component of the system. The triggering threshold identified for the activation of the warning system is based on the 1-year return period level, whereas return periods from 2 to 50 years were used as reference to design the TWL extreme scenarios of the flood and impact catalogues. The reason behind choosing a “high probability” return period is based on the consideration that such events can also generate significant losses and damages.

Some respondents asked for additional, low probability return periods to be considered (200-, 250-, and 1,000-year return periods). Such return periods were not addressed in the framework of the project because of the available hindcast period, which covered only 10 years, that is considered sufficient to properly estimate return levels associated to only 20-50-year return periods. It is interesting to note that coastal flood mapping products of such low probability are presented in the EU Member States submissions for the first (and second) implementation cycles of the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC, which mostly consider floods triggered by medium and low probability storm events (D2.2, Velegrakis et al., 2021). The above suggests that: a) products associated with low-probability events should be taken into account in the Roadmap (Deliverable 6.4 – Roadmap of ECFAS integration into CEMS); and b) the ECFAS products associated to high and medium probability events (1 to 50 years) can close a significant gap in the information related to the coastal flood hazard.

The flood products have received high importance gradings from the respondents (Question 28, Annex B). End users from public organisations appear to be keener than the other user groups for some products. Regarding the flood maps themselves, the most preferred option for spatial resolution is 25 m, although the 50 and 100 m spatial resolutions are also chosen by a significant fraction of the respondents. The ECFAS coastal flood map catalogue (Deliverable 5.4 – Pan-EU flood maps catalogue) will include Pan-European flood extension, depth and velocity with a resolution of 100 m. This selection takes into account the potential users’ preferences, computational demands and the flood model validation work carried out within the framework of WP5 (Deliverable 5.2 – Validated LISFLOOD-FP model for coastal areas, Le Gal et al. 2021).

A major objective of the questionnaire survey was to gauge the awareness of potential end-users of the most relevant policies and legislation identified in ECFAS D2.2 – Coastal Climate Resilience: Review of Policies and

Regulations (Velegrakis et al., 2021). The survey results associated with the familiarity of the potential ECFAS end-users with very significant policies and legislation related to the assessment and management of coastal flooding are disheartening and represent an ongoing challenge. It appears that there is limited familiarity/awareness across the board, with a particular lack or low awareness of significant policy and legal instruments. Particularly noteworthy is the low familiarity of the potential end-users related to the SFDRR 2015-2030 and the associated EU SFDRR Action Plan, as well as the limited familiarity with the FD (2007/60/EC). Both SFDRR and the associated EU SFDRR Action Plan provide the overarching policy framework for DRR, promote the mainstreaming of risk assessments/mapping, and prescribe targets for EWS availability/access. The latter is the most significant EU legal instrument on the assessment and management of (coastal) floods.

Flood risk reduction in the coastal zone requires development and availability of pertinent tools and data. It also needs to be underpinned by strong and synergetic policy and legal frameworks. Policies define and formulate ambition, objectives and commitments, whereas legal instruments are powerful tools for the implementation of policy objectives. However, in order for these frameworks to be effective, awareness by decision makers and other stakeholders is required so that they are mainstreamed in all Disaster Risk Reduction phases and plans. The end-user questionnaire survey suggests that although there are policy and legislation frameworks for the assessment and management of the coastal flood risk, their effectiveness is likely to be constrained by the limited familiarity of a large swath of stakeholders. It appears that there should be sustained efforts to increase the knowledge of the ECFAS potential end-users (and other related stakeholders) on the emerging policy imperatives and existing legal obligations.

Regarding the statistics used in the D2.3, limitations in statistical studies might always be encountered, as for example, those that characterised the present sample (e.g., the geographical distribution of users and types of their parent organisations). Nevertheless, it is important to consider the objectives of ECFAS (to develop products and tools for the evolution of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service in the coastal areas) and the objective of the Deliverable 2.3. The consultation proved to be a crucial tool in identifying end-users’ needs and requirements; the results of the questionnaire survey contributed largely to the development of ECFAS products and provided insights on the limitations, challenges and opportunities for the evolution of a European Coastal Flood Awareness System and other related services in the future.

Copernicus and its various services are user-driven. Potential users’ needs and requirements can affect the decisions taken at the top of the value chain whereas end-users benefit from its fit-for-purpose services. Therefore, the end-users’ contribution/feedback are crucial for the original design, as well as the subsequent improvements of the ECFAS system.

The results presented in Deliverable 2.3 provide much-needed information for both the ECFAS development and its potential integration into CEMS. ECFAS will contribute information for emergency response and risk management and will broaden the exploitation of related Copernicus services within a range of entities.

The collation of the potential user and survey respondent pools has been a very important step towards the wide gauging of relevant user needs and requirements. However, these pools are dominated by public sector personnel from Southern and Mediterranean European Countries. As it is important that the needs/requirements of a broader audience in terms of geographical location and work sector are considered, there should be a continuous outreach effort to the other European coastal regions (the North, Baltic and Black Seas) as well as to organisations that are instrumental for the uptaking/using of coastal flood awareness systems, such as civil protection agencies.

Potential end-users appear to be interested in what ECFAS has to offer, specifically:

- coastal hazard warnings/forecasts (for total water levels, storm surge levels, and waves), which are ECFAS core outputs and integrated in the other system products; and
- a full range of warning and mapping products (e.g., flood extent, depth and flow velocity, shoreline positions prior to and following extreme events).

Moreover, user needs/requirements in terms of the specifications of a coastal flood awareness system (regarding e.g., event return periods, forecast lead times, time frequency updates, spatial resolutions of the flood forcing and impacts) are now embedded in the final ECFAS products.

There should be sustained efforts to increase stakeholder familiarity to the EU policy imperatives and existing legal obligations in the assessment and management of coastal flood risks, as well as the engagement of end-users.

5 References

- Álvarez-Fanjul, E., de Pascual Collar, Á., Pérez Gómez, B., De Alfonso, M., García Sotillo, M., Staneva, J., Clementi, E., Grandi, A., Zacharioudaki, A., Korres, G., Ravdas, M., Renshaw, R., Tinker, J., Raudsepp, U., Lagemaa, P., Maljutenko, I., Geyer, G., Müller M., Çaglar Yumruktepe, V., 2019. Sea level, sea surface temperature and SWH extreme percentiles: combined analysis from model results and in situ observations. In: Copernicus Marine Service Ocean State Report, Issue 3. *Journal of Operational Oceanography* 12:sup1, s31–s43. doi: 10.1080/1755876X.2019.1633075
- Andrews, D., Nonnecke, B., Preece, J., 2003. Electronic Survey Methodology: A Case Study in Reaching Hard-to-Involve Internet Users. *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, 16(2):185-210. doi: 10.1207/S15327590IJHC1602_04
- Armaroli, C. and Duo, E., 2018. Validation of the coastal storm risk assessment framework along the Emilia-Romagna coast. *Coastal Engineering*, 134, 159-167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2017.08.014>
- Armaroli, C., Duo, E., Viavattene, C., 2019. From hazard to consequences: evaluation of direct and indirect impacts of flooding along the Emilia-Romagna coastline, Italy. *Frontiers in Earth Science, Geohazards and Georisks*, 7, 203, doi: 10.3389/feart.2019.00203
- Armaroli, C., Schiavon, E., Dufau, C., Ieronymidi, E., 2021. Summary and Statistics of users engagement activities – ECFAS Project (GA 101004211), www.ecfas.eu
- Asariotis R., Benamara H., Mohos-Naray, V., 2017. Port industry survey on climate change impacts and adaptation. UNCTAD Research Paper No 18. UNCTAD/SER.RP/2018/18/Rev.1. https://unctad.org/en/PublicationsLibrary/ser-rp-2017d18_en.pdf
- Daniel, M. J., Hogan, J.W., 2008. *Missing Data in Longitudinal Studies Strategies for Bayesian Modeling and Sensitivity Analysis*. London: Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Deeks J.J., Higgins J.P.T., Altman D.G. (editors) on behalf of the Cochrane Statistical Methods Group. Chapter 9: Analysing data and undertaking meta-analyses. In: Higgins J.P.T., Churchill R., Chandler J., Cumpston M.S. (editors), *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 5.2.0 (updated June 2017), Cochrane, 2017. Available from www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.
- Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, OJ 1995 L 281/31.

- ECFAS project, 2021. D6.1 ECFAS Platform architecture and design document– ECFAS Project (GA 101004211), www.ecfas.eu
- Eleveld, M.A., Schrimpf, W.B.H., Siegert, A.G., 2003. User requirements and information definition for a virtual coastal and marine data warehouse. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 46:(6-7),487–505. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-5691\(03\)00031-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0964-5691(03)00031-0)
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, 2017. Interim evaluation of Copernicus: final report, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/373088>
- European Commission, 2019. Expression of User Needs for the Copernicus Programme https://www.copernicus.eu/sites/default/files/2019-10/STAFF_WORKING_PAPER_2019-394-Expression_of_User_Needs_for_the_Copernicus_Programme.pdf
- European Court of Auditors, 2021. Special Report 07/2021: EU space programmes Galileo and Copernicus: services launched, but the uptake needs a further boost. <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eca/special-reports/space-programmes-7-2021/en/>
- Fernández-Montblanc, T., Vousdoukas, M.I., Ciavola, P., Voukouvalas, E., Mentaschi, L., Breyiannis, G., Feyen, L., Salamon, P., 2019. Towards robust pan-European storm surge forecasting. *Ocean Modelling* 133, 129-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocemod.2018.12.001>
- García-Medina G., Özkan-Haller H.T., Ruggiero P., Holman R.A., Nicolini T., 2018. Analysis and catalogue of sneaker waves in the US Pacific Northwest between 2005 and 2017. *Natural Hazards* 94, 583–603
- Geraldini S., Bruschi A., Bellotti G., Taramelli, A., 2021. User Needs Analysis for the Definition of Operational Coastal Services. *Water* 13(1):92. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13010092>
- Holman, R.A., Sallenger, A.H., 1985. Setup and swash on a natural beach. *Journal of Geophysical Research.*, 90(C1):945-953. <http://doi.wiley.com/10.1029/JC090iC01p00945>
- Ieronymidi, E. and Grigoriadis, D., 2021. Guidelines for D3.1 - Coastal dataset including exposure and vulnerability layers, Deliverable 3.1 – ECFAS Project (GA 101004211), www.ecfas.eu. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5802094>
- Joubert-Boitat, I., Wania, A., Dalmaso S., 2020. Manual for CEMS-Rapid Mapping Products. EUR 30370 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. doi:10.2760/29876, JRC121741
- Le Gal, M., Ciavola, P., Gastal, V., Fernández -Montblanc,T., Delbour, S., 2021. Validated LISFLOOD-FP model for coastal areas, Deliverable 5.2 – ECFAS Project (GA 101004211) www.ecfas.eu. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5809291>

- Kempf, L. K., 2005. Encyclopaedia of social measurement. Amsterdam: Elsevier/Academic Press.
- Legeais, J.-F, Prandi, P., Labroue, S., Guerou, A., Shaw, A., 2021. Consortium Members ESA Sea-Level CCI+Sea-Level in Coastal Areas: User Requirement Document. Available at https://climate.esa.int/media/documents/SLCCI_URD_005_UserRequirementsDoc_v1.3.pdf
- Matevosyan, H., Lluch, I., Poghosyan, A., Golkar, A., 2017. A Value-Chain Analysis for the Copernicus Earth Observation Infrastructure Evolution: A Knowledgebase of Users, Needs, Services, and Products," IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine 5(3):19-35. doi 10.1109/MGRS.2017.2720263
- Pardo-Pascual, J.E., Palomar-Vázquez, J., Cabezas-Rabadán C., Almonacid-Caballer, J., Fernández Sarría, A., Souto-Ceccon, P.E., Montes-Pérez, J., 2021. Report on algorithms for the extraction of satellite derived shorelines. Deliverable 3.2 - Algorithms for satellite derived shoreline mapping and shorelines dataset, ECFAS Project (GA 101004211), www.ecfas.eu
- Pérez, F.F., Fanjul, E.Á., Hernández, J.D., Julián Delgado Hernández, Sanz, N.V., Fletcher, A.G., Sánchez, R.M., Santamaría, R.M., 2020. Data services for intermediate users at the coastal zone: analysis of gaps and recommendations for evolution from the Spanish perspective. Available at <https://insitu.copernicus.eu/library/reports/data-services-for-intermediate-users-at-the-coastal-zone-spanish-perspective>
- Roth P.L., BeVier C.A., 1998. Response rates in HRM/OB survey research: norms and correlates, 1990-1994. Journal of Management 24(1):97-117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639802400107>
- Schumann, G. J.-P., Brakenridge, G.R., Kettner, A.J., Kashif, R., Niebuhr, E., 2018. Assisting Flood Disaster Response with Earth Observation Data and Products: A Critical Assessment Remote Sensing 10(8):1230. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10081230>
- Sheremet, A., Staples, T., Arduin, F., Suanez, S., Fichaut, B., 2014. Observations of large infragravity wave runup at Banneg island, France. Geophysical Research Letters 41 (3), 976–982.
- StataCorp. 2021.Stata Statistical Software: Release 17. College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC.
- Stockdon, H.F., Holman, R.A., Howd, P.A., Sallenger, J.A.H., 2006. Empirical parameterization of setup, swash, and runup. Coastal Engineering 53 (7), 573–588. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2005.12.005>.
- Stockdon, H.F., Thompson, D.M., Plant, N.G., Long, I.W., 2014. Evaluation of wave runup predictions from numerical and parametric models. Coastal Engineering 92, 1-11
- Velegrakis, A.F., Hasiotis, T., Papadatou, K., 2021. Coastal climate resilience: review of policies and regulations, Deliverable 2.2 – ECFAS Project (GA 101004211), www.ecfas.eu

Annex A: Questionnaire

Section A - Stakeholder screening: generic questions about user role.

1. Are you a public or a private user?

- A. Public
- B. Private
- C. Other. Please, specify in the comment box.

2. Please, identify your organisation in one of these categories:

- | | | |
|------------------------|------------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| A. National authority | G. Environmental protection agency | L. EU agency or research centre |
| B. University | H. International organisation | M. EU directorate |
| C. Research institute | I. Civil protection | N. NGO/Association |
| D. Private company/SME | J. Municipality | O. International agency |
| E. Large enterprise | K. Private citizen | |
| F. Regional authority | | |

3. Country of your organisation:

4. At what administrative/geographical level does your organisation work?

- | | |
|---------------------|------------------------|
| A. Municipal level. | D. Pan-European level |
| B. Regional level. | E. International level |
| C. National level. | |

5. What natural hazards do you mainly deal with? You can select multiple answers.

- | | | |
|---------------------|-------------------------|---|
| A. Coastal flooding | H. Tropical cyclones | O. Wildfires |
| B. Coastal erosion | I. Windstorms | P. Droughts |
| C. Storm surge | J. Marine storms | Q. Earthquakes |
| D. River flooding | K. Heavy precipitations | R. Volcanic activity |
| E. Flash-floods | L. Heatwaves | S. Other. Please, specify in the comment box. |
| F. Landslides | M. Cold spells | |
| G. Tsunamis | N. Forest fires | |

6. How familiar are you with the following concepts? Please, rank your answer from 1 not familiar to 10 very familiar.

- | | |
|------------------|----------------------------------|
| A. Probability | G. Spatial and temporal coverage |
| B. Return period | H. Vulnerability |
| C. Uncertainty | I. Risk |
| D. Accuracy | J. Hazard |
| E. Resolution | K. Impact |
| F. Forecast | L. Exposure |

7. Are you a current user of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service?

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. I do not know this service

8. Are you a current user of the European Flood Awareness System?

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. I do not know this service

Section B - Coastal awareness system

9. Are you currently using a coastal awareness/early warning system?
- A. Yes
 - B. No

If YES, please, answer the next questions. Otherwise go to question 14.

10. This service is provided by: (You can select multiple answers.)

- A. A regional governmental organisation
- B. A national government
- C. A European public service
- D. A non-European public service
- E. I produce this service inside my organisation
- F. I purchase the service from a private provider
- G. I obtain the service from a research institute or university
- H. Other. Please, specify in the comment box.

11. Does the service you use provide an evaluation of the impact on the coastal area?

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. I do not know

12. Which of the following elements are present in the service you currently use? You can select multiple answers.

- A. Wave climate forecast
- B. Total water level forecast
- C. Flood maps
- D. Exposure and/or vulnerability information
- E. Impact Assessment
- F. Other. Please, specify in the comment box.

13. What are the major **limitations** in the service you are currently using and what kind of **improvements** do you need?

14. How important is a Pan-European Coastal Flood Awareness System for your organisation?

- | | | |
|------------------------|-----------------------|--------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Important |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat important | |

15. For which activities would you use a coastal flood-awareness and impact-assessment system? You can select multiple answers.

- A. Analysis of the evolution of the coastline
- B. Exposure evaluation of the coastal area
- C. Provision and/or analysis of coastal flood maps
- D. Impact assessment on population
- E. Impact assessment on the built environment (e.g., buildings, infrastructure, etc.)
- F. Impact assessment on seaports and navigation
- G. Impacts on ecosystems and natural environment
- H. Monitoring of the natural environment and ecosystem services
- I. Marine-coastal forecasts (wave climate, oceanographic variables)
- J. Monitoring of extreme total sea levels for the study of coastal erosion
- K. Monitoring of extreme total sea levels for the study of coastal flooding
- L. Impact mapping in the emergency phase
- M. Emergency response activities
- N. Evaluation of potential technical adaptation measures
- O. Other. Please, specify in the comment box.

16. How important is it to you to receive the information in your native language (other than English)?

- | | | |
|------------------------|-----------------------|--------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Essential |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat essential | |

Section C - ECFAS warning components

17. What is the importance of each product for your work? Please, rank your answer from 1 not important to 10 very important. No answer = unknown terminology.

- A. Total water level (mean sea level, tidal level, storm surge and wave setup levels)
- B. Storm surge
- C. Wave climate (wave height, wave period and wave direction)
- D. Wave runup
- E. Flood map (flood extension, water depth and water velocity)

18. What is the minimum acceptable **spatial resolution (in metres)** for **total water level** (mean sea level, tidal level, storm surge and wave setup levels), **storm surge**, **wave climate** (wave height, wave period and wave direction), and **wave runup** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

- | | | |
|----------|------------|------------|
| A. 100 m | C. 500 m | E. 3,000 m |
| B. 300 m | D. 1,000 m | F. 5,000 m |

19. What is the minimum acceptable **spatial resolution (in metres)** for a **flood map** (flood extension, water depth and water velocity) for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

- | | | |
|----------|------------|------------|
| A. 25 m | D. 300 m | G. 3,000 m |
| B. 50 m | E. 500 m | H. 5,000 m |
| C. 100 m | F. 1,000 m | |

20. What is the minimum acceptable **time frequency update (in hours)** for **total water level**, **storm surge**, **wave climate**, **wave runup**, and **flood map** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

- | | | |
|-----------|----------|---------|
| A. 24 hrs | C. 6 hrs | E. 1 hr |
| B. 12 hrs | D. 2 hrs | |

21. What is the minimum acceptable **forecast lead time (in days)** for **total water level**, **storm surge**, **wave climate**, **wave runup**, and **flood map** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

- | | | |
|-----------|-----------|------------|
| A. 1 day | C. 3 days | E. 10 days |
| B. 2 days | D. 5 days | F. 30 days |

22. Please, evaluate from 1 to 10 (1 = not important; 10 = very important; No answer = unknown/unfamiliar with the concept) the importance of the following storm events probability for your work.

- | | |
|--|---|
| A. Events with a return period \approx 500 years | D. Events with a return period \approx 10 years |
| B. Events with a return period \approx 100 years | E. Events with a return period \approx 5 years |
| C. Events with a return period \approx 50 years | F. Events with a return period \approx 1 year |

23. Are there other storm event probabilities that you consider important for your work purposes? If **YES**, please list them.

24. Are there storm event probabilities considered of importance by your national protection service? If **YES**, please list them.

Section D - Importance of coastal exposure and vulnerability assessment.

25. Do you currently evaluate coastal flood exposure and/or vulnerability?

- A. Yes
- B. No

If NO, please, go to question 27.

26. How important are the following elements to evaluate exposure and vulnerability for impact assessment? Please, rank your answer from 1 not important to 10 very important.

- A. Population
- B. Buildings
- C. Commercial and industrial activities
- D. Infrastructure and transport networks
- E. Agriculture
- F. Ecosystems
- G. Cultural heritage
- H. Utility networks (gas, electricity, water, etc.)

27. For the activities you perform, how useful is it to conduct a social vulnerability assessment for coastal flood risk reduction?

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Extremely useful |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat useful | |

Section E - ECFAS mapping products

28. What type of mapping products are more important for you? Please, evaluate each product from 1 not important to 10 very important.

- A. Pre- and post-event shoreline position detection
- B. Post-event shoreline displacement magnitude
- C. Monitoring of temporal evolution of the shoreline position after events
- D. Pre- and post-event beach width dimension
- E. Post-event magnitude of beach width change
- F. Identification of erosional hot-spots
- G. Post-disaster coastal erosion risk assessment
- H. Impact assessment on population and assets
- I. Modelled flood extent
- J. Detailed damage assessment analysis over affected areas
- K. Event-based coastal flood notifications
- L. Coastal defence structures layer
- M. Vulnerable population mapping
- N. Information on relevant meteorological conditions (e.g., winds)
- O. Assessment of coastal and marine flood map forecasting skills
- P. Geographical information (e.g., administrative boundaries, presence of river mouths)

Section F -Relevant policy and legislation issues

29. How familiar are you with the following policies and legislation relevant to coastal flooding risk?

Please, rank from 1 not familiar to 10 very familiar.

- | | |
|--|---|
| A. The 2015 Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) | H. The EU Directive 2000/60/EC (Water Framework Directive) |
| B. The 2008 Protocol to the Barcelona Convention on Integrated Coastal Zone Management | I. The EU Directive 2003/4/EC on Public Access to Environmental Information |
| C. The EU Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation (2021) | J. The EU Directive 2007/60/EC on the assessment and management of flood risks |
| D. The EU Action Plan on SFDRR 2015–2030 | K. The EU Directive 2007/2/EC on the EU Spatial Information infrastructure (INSPIRE Directive) |
| E. The EU Civil Protection Mechanism - UCPM (Decision No. 1313/2013/EU) | L. The EU Directive 2014/52/EU on the assessment of the effects of certain public/private projects on the environment (amended EIA Directive) |
| F. The EU Climate Law (2021) | |
| G. The Directive 92/43/EEC on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna/flora | |

30. How do you rate ECFAS in terms of its contribution towards disaster risk reduction in coastal areas?

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Extremely useful |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat useful | |

31. How useful is a coastal flood awareness system for the implementation of the following policies presented in the 2021 EU Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation? Please, rate your answer from 1 not useful to 10 very useful:

- A. Regulation and funding should consider Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) to avoid new exposure
- B. Closing of knowledge gaps and capacity building/training to respond to climatic hazards
- C. Availability of relevant data and mechanisms to coordinate disaster risk management
- D. Data availability/usability from EU scientific lighthouses and translation of information to user-friendly tools

32. How relevant are ECFAS products for monitoring the shoreline position?

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Extremely useful |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat useful | |

Section G - Concluding questions

33. How useful would it be to include a catalogue for available products in ECFAS?

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| A. Irrelevant | C. Neutral | E. Extremely useful |
| B. Somewhat irrelevant | D. Somewhat useful | |

34. How useful would it be to include an archive for available products in ECFAS?

- | | | |
|------------------------|--------------------|---------------------|
| F. Irrelevant | H. Neutral | J. Extremely useful |
| G. Somewhat irrelevant | I. Somewhat useful | |

35. What is your knowledge level regarding the following geospatial information formats? Please, rank your answer from 1 poor knowledge to 10 very good knowledge.

- | | |
|---------------------------------|-----------------------|
| A. Shapefile (.shp) | E. Geo TIFF |
| B. Txt, dbf, ASCII, and similar | F. CSV |
| C. GeoJSON | G. Geopackage (.gpkg) |
| D. NetCDF | |

36. What use would you make of a platform for Coastal Flood Awareness? You can select multiple answers.

- | | |
|--------------------|---|
| A. Inform | D. Other. Please, specify in the comment box. |
| B. Decide | |
| C. Raise awareness | |

37. Are you interested to test the ECFAS system at sites of your interest?

- A. Yes
- B. No

38. What is the best communication channel through which we can share ECFAS updates with you?

Multiple choice allowed

- A. Newsletter
- B. Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn)
- C. Website
- D. Events
- E. Other. Please, specify in the comment box

Annex B: Results of the questionnaire survey

Section A - Stakeholder screening: generic questions about user role

1. Are you a public or a private user?

- Other: consultant; researcher; representative of a professional body; and NGO.

2. Please, identify your organisation in one of these categories:

3. Country of your organisation:

Country	n	%
Italy	27	23.1
Spain	16	13.7
France	15	12.8
Greece	13	11.1
Ireland	8	6.8
UK	8	6.8
Portugal	4	3.4
Belgium	3	2.6
Cyprus	2	1.7
Malta	2	1.7
Europe	2	1.7
Germany	2	1.7
Poland	2	1.7
Croatia	1	0.9
Slovenia	1	0.9
Denmark	1	0.9
Finland	1	0.9
Netherlands	1	0.9
Romania	1	0.9
Switzerland	1	0.9
Brazil	1	0.9
India	1	0.9
Malaysia	1	0.9
Morocco	1	0.9
Peru	1	0.9
Tunisia	1	0.9

4. At what administrative/geographical level does your organisation work?

5. What natural hazards do you mainly deal with? You can select multiple answers.

Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

- Other: subsidence, sea-level rise; pluvial floods; technology risks; network survey; global operational oceanography.

6. How familiar are you with the following concepts? Ranking from 1 (unfamiliar) to 5 (very familiar).

7. Are you a current user of the Copernicus Emergency Management Service?

8. Are you a current user of the European Flood Awareness System?

Section B - Coastal awareness system

9. Are you currently using a coastal awareness/early warning system?

If YES, please, answer the next questions. Otherwise go to question 14.

10. Service provider: (You can select multiple answers.)

Responses based on n = 35, i.e., respondents that responded “Yes” to question 9. Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

- Other: “SHOM contributes to the service as (i) the provider of tide information and sea surface height observations from its tide gauge network, and (ii) through the scientific applied development and operational implementation of the ocean modelling capability of storm surge and coastal waves, underlying the service”.

11. Does the service you use provide an evaluation of the impact on the coastal area?

Responses based on n = 35, i.e., respondents that responded “Yes” to question 9. Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

12. Which of the following elements are present in the service you currently use? You can select multiple answers.

Responses based on n = 35, i.e., respondents that responded “Yes” to question 9. Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

- Other: localise flood indicators for crisis management (e.g., road trafficability); flood maps and impacts; risk data available from other sources/programmes; flood maps —but they are provided by the Finnish Environmental Institute; storm surge and astronomical tide; and network.

13. What are the major **limitations** in the service you are currently using and what kind of **improvements** do you need?

- Responses based on n = 35, i.e., respondents that responded “Yes” to question 9.
 - a. The service provided by the national government is an early warning system for marine storms. The information is not precise at the local scale (for management purposes) and it is not providing TWL. The database produced by the University of Brest consists of a set of indicators for vulnerability to coastal erosion and marine flooding comprising indicators on hazards, exposed elements, management policies and risk perception. It is available at the scale of Brittany, except for management indicators at the scale of Finistère and risk perception indicators at the scale of several cities.
 - b. Temporal assessment, spatial accuracy, post-impact provision.
 - c. No information on inland flood characteristics (map, intensity, etc.); limited spatial extent.
 - d. Punctual evaluation, it does not include real impacts and an expert analysis is needed.
 - e. Impact assessment.
 - f. There still is no operational mapping of potentially flooded areas within this Early Warning System.
 - g. Climatological data is needed (including a database of events and related impacts at the local scale).
 - h. It does not provide any coastal risks.
 - i. Exhaustive impact assessment.
 - j. Limitations of National Tide and Storm Surge Forecasting Service:
 - No wave conditions forecast
 - No wave set-up effect forecast
 - System uses one source of forecast input data (ECMWF) only, which is deterministic.
 - System is only updated at 12-hour intervals.
 - System does not presently run in a high-performance computing operational centre
 - k. Impact assessment is still limited. There is no operational mapping of potentially flooded area. Need more climatological data (including database of events and related impacts at the local scales).

- l. Flooded area forecasts (maximum water envelop, maximum water height, etc.), past extreme events database with full characterisation (met-ocean forcing conditions, post-event model re-analysis, impacted areas, damages, statistical representativeness).
- m. Forecast driven impact assessment.
- n. Improvements: wave and water level scaling at local scale, 2-D approach, monitoring, annual topo-bathymetry surveys.
- o. It is important to be able to transfer relevant information from the level of operational marine weather forecasts to the level of impacts on the coast (both at the urban scale and on the natural environment). This can only be done by refining reliable (not overly simplified) impact models on the coast, possibly validated, with a level of detail at least representative of urban scales.
- p. Predictability for several days in advance should be improved, one way would be multi-model ensembles for atmosphere and ocean.
- q. Coastal predictions, which are generated as a "side product" of our organisation's main area of interest (navigable rivers in Flanders, including tidal river Scheldt) are used by the Flemish organisation responsible for warnings of high tides at the coast.
- r. Inland wave spreading and its impact.
- s. Wave climate, wave effects, and impact assessments are currently not included.
- t. The data update cycle.
- u. There is a need to improve a 1 to 3-day flood forecast accuracy.

14. How important is a Pan-European Coastal Flood Awareness System for your organisation?

15. For which activities would you use a coastal flood-awareness and impact-assessment system? You can select multiple answers.

- Other: risk assessment; future sea-level rise impact on potential risks of coastal flooding and erosion in relation to the built environment, infrastructure and high-value industrial assets.

16. How important is it to you to receive the information in your native language (other than English)?

Section C - ECFAS warning components

17. What is the importance of each product for your work? Ranking from 1 (unimportant) to 5 (very important). No answer (N/A) = unknown terminology.

18. What is the minimum acceptable **spatial resolution (in metres)** for **total water level, storm surge, wave climate, and wave runup** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

19. What is the minimum acceptable **spatial resolution (in metres)** for a **flood map** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

20. What is the minimum acceptable **time frequency update (in hours)** for **total water level, storm surge, wave climate, wave runup, and flood map** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

21. What is the minimum acceptable **forecast lead time (in days)** for **total water level, storm surge, wave climate, wave runup, and flood map** for a Pan-European coastal flood awareness system?

22. What is the importance of the following storm events probability for your work? Evaluation from 1 (unimportant) to 5 (very important). No answer (N/A) = unknown terminology

23. Are there other storm event probabilities that you consider important for your work purposes? If **YES**, please list them.

- a) 2- year return period;
- b) 2-, 20-, 200-year return periods;
- c) 200-year return period, this is usually used for coastal defences design in the UK;
- d) 200- and 250-year return period;
- e) 1,000-year return period;
- f) climate change influence;
- g) approximate probability of cyclones;
- h) sea-storm persistence (length in hours);
- i) estuarine river flooding due to precipitation and sea-level rise.

24. Are there storm event probabilities considered of importance by your national protection service? If **YES**, please list them.

- a) 2-year return period or higher;
- b) 100-year return period;
- c) 200-year return period;
- d) 1,000-year return period;
- e) 100- and 1,000-year return period;
- f) higher than 10-year return period;
- g) 2-, 5-, 10-, 20-, 50-, 100-, 200-, 500-, and 1000-year return period;
- h) events included in the EU Floods Directive;
- i) number of sea storms, their peak features, direction, and persistence, impact of climate change on sea storms, and coastal flooding;
- j) 1,000-, 4,000-, and 10,000-year return periods;
- k) water level rising higher than the pre-defined water considered by warning levels.

Section D - Importance of coastal exposure and vulnerability assessment.

25. Do you currently evaluate coastal flood exposure and/or vulnerability?

If NO, please, go to question 27.

26. How important are the following elements to evaluate exposure and vulnerability for impact assessment? Ranking from 1 (unimportant) to 5 (very important).

Responses based on n = 62, i.e., respondents that responded “Yes” to question 25. Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

27. For the activities you perform, how useful is it to conduct a social vulnerability assessment for coastal flood risk reduction?

Section E - ECFAS mapping products

28. What type of mapping products are more important for you? Evaluation from 1 (unimportant) to 5 (very important).

Section F - Relevant policy and legislation issues

29. How familiar are you with the following policies and legislation relevant to coastal flooding risk? Ranking from 1 (unfamiliar) to 5 (very familiar).

30. How do you rate ECFAS in terms of its contribution towards disaster risk reduction in coastal areas?

31. How useful is a coastal flood awareness system for the implementation of the following policies presented in the 2021 EU Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation? Rating from 1 (irrelevant) to 5 (very useful).

32. How relevant are ECFAS products for monitoring the shoreline position?

Section G - Concluding questions

33. How useful would it be to include a catalogue for available products in ECFAS?

34. How useful would it be to include an archive for available products in ECFAS?

35. What is your knowledge level regarding the following geospatial information formats?
Please, rank your answer from 1 unknowledgeable to 5 very knowledgeable.

36. What use would you make of a platform for Coastal Flood Awareness? You can select multiple answers.

Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

- Other: to advise, to schedule local actions, to complete EFAS, to use as boundary conditions for high-resolution flood modelling, for post-event assessment, as a comparison with our own system, to survey, to plan civil protection responses, to research.

37. Are you interested to test the ECFAS system at sites of your interest?

38. What is the best communication channel through which we can share ECFAS updates with you? Multiple choice allowed.

Chart represents absolute numbers (n).

- Other: virtual platform, virtual events, and training sessions.